
PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEM FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF FAMILIAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS

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Annotation.

this article is an important factor in the role of parents in raising children in the family, the relationship between a student, brother and sister, the development of personality in the family, the role of the family in society.

Keywords.

are the development of personality, familistic competence, ambition, upbringing of boys, the role of the parent, the foundation of the personality in the family, different periods of family life.

In the development of the familial competence of students, the upbringing of student-young people is considered very important therefore, in the upbringing of children, usually the father is more engaged in the upbringing of boys. Of course, it is important to take into account the level of the child. Therefore, in boys, it is necessary to develop and implement training programs aimed at the formation of qualities, entrepreneurial and family skills, such as love for the motherland, loyalty to the National idea, courage, courage, self-sacrifice, honesty, truthfulness, needlessness, conscientiousness, restraint, youth pride, or dishonesty, kindness. Extensive absorption of knowledge, skills and competencies into the content of education, which serves to form the indicators and competencies of spiritual education in students through the subject of “upbringing” the collective foundations of the formation of familial competence of boys of teenage age on the basis of the program of the concept of continuous moral education;

strengthening of the motive for striving for success as a priority feature of the individual;

strengthening the conscious control of the child's own behavior and activities;

to react to the behavior, behavior of himself and those around him, to teach hard work;

the emergence of social motives for cooperation with adults and peers;

expansion, deepening of knowledge, development of spiritual and moral skills and competencies;

manifestation of interest in the traditions, values of their own people and other peoples;

strengthening safe life skills;

expanding ideas about professions, interest in the profession and work;

teaching conscientious work skills, showing the importance of labor in the life of a person and society;

enriching the experience of spiritual and moral relations with peers;

moral, political worldview and the formation of religious beliefs;

the transformation of social competence and qualities necessary for an independent life into habits.

As a result of the father's reluctance, inability to fulfill his duty, teach useful knowledge and good deeds, he cannot form the necessary positive qualities in his child. The child also grows up priceless from the good upbringing of his father. The next period requires some demand and discipline. This period is adolescence, when the child separates white and black. From this stage, he learns that reward for good, punishment for evil is inevitable. During this period, it is considered an important step for a child to be a decent, good person if he is properly guided, accompanied by knowledgeable friends. Usually mothers try to hide the mistakes and shortcomings of their children from their father. I say, they beat, they do not tell the father about the mistakes he made, the evils he did. As a result, the child can commit more serious crimes without fear after not receiving a timely reprimand.

It is also necessary to keep the norm when giving affection. Doing what the child says to everyone, approving all the right and wrong behavior, even being silent, causes the child to grow up completely uneducated. Excessive pampering weakens the child in every possible way, while showing affection encourages him to be more active. Growing up in a family with indifference, the child grows up irresponsible, selfish. Mother's service is very necessary and important in the upbringing of the child as a competent person.

The most important tool in upbringing is to educate a child with affection and sweetness. These two tools make up one thing. In particular, it is better not to do education with anger and punishment. After all, compulsory education quickly disappears from the memory of a teenage child. As a result, his interest in this area may subside. It is clear that the beginning of Education also begins with good upbringing.

Today, one of the social problems in raising a child, especially in the upbringing of teenage students, is cell phone harassment and growing intellectually by studying social networks. While these modern means of communication are an important means of communication, they have a negative impact on some teenage youth whose spirituality is not fully formed. Parents, together with educational institutions, should explain the true nature of the means of communication to young people affected by the social network.

Negative influence from outside of parenthood is the greatest risk. Because when a child is not given freedom in this regard in the family, he begins to look outside for reasons that satisfy his interests and incentives. This means that parents should also pay serious attention to the external life of their child. That is, they need to control where their child goes after school or college, what he does. Another method that parents can use as a tool in teaching their child to spend their time efficiently is the rational use of modern information technology. It is important that the parent takes his child with him to beautiful places of nature, museums, while instilling beauty in his soul.

Many scientists note that the period required for a young family to strengthen and get on their feet, independently solve various household problems on its own, in fact, is directly related to the sincere attitude of two married individuals towards each other, their harmonious views on different values in the family and its surroundings, their skill to be able to apply in their family

But still, each family experiences certain difficulties precisely at a young age, these problems manifest themselves in such a way that they depend on the following situations: lack of time to ensure that family life goes smoothly, work, study or solve other issues;

good time, limited entertainment;

in the new conditions, a man is also physically exhausted by a woman, nervous exhaustion;

economic difficulties.

The last 2 of the listed cases can negatively affect the behavior of a child of adolescent age.

In many families, we can observe that in most cases, when the mother is a wise and sweet word, girls also get a good upbringing. The fact that a man is intelligent, without success, the boy's growth, incompetence, difficulty finding his place in life

are encountered. This is a sign that social control in the family, in the upbringing of a boy in surroundings, has subsided.

The fundamental function of a woman in the family, on the other hand, is to be able to give birth and raise a child, conduct a fast, correctly distribute family funds, family budget according to the needs of family members.

It is also the duties of the mother to cultivate, chivalry, the formation of aesthetic taste, hard work and sympathy in the minds and behavior of children. Together with this, there are also tasks for representatives of both sexes to be able to avoid possible conflicts that arise in the family.

Until recently, one fact that existed in the Uzbek family was such that the role of the mother was great in the formation of the personality of the child, raising him mentally, mentally, physically healthy. In short, a certain part of the spiritual support of the family lies with the woman. The father was not directly involved in the upbringing of the child, but often the mother used the personality of the father in the process of upbringing. For example: our mothers say "I tell your father," we discourage children from bad work, "how do we tell your father?" meant the degree of evil in what we did, and in doing so increased the power of our father's influence on us. When raising a child, the mother was given the father's personality, authority. The father, on the other hand, was directly involved in the upbringing process in case of emergency or when the child's Act received a "snack". Before that, the process was controlled through the mother.

Even today, the fact that we do not lose this position of the father in the family indicates that we are not indifferent to the fate of the nation, people and society.

The latter situation is explained, on the one hand, by the increase in the desire of boys in teenage years at the same time, and on the other hand, by the increase in the expenditure associated with the desire of parents, went-came. Despite the fact that day after day our living and living conditions improve in Uzbekistan and there are enough conditions for the well-being of the family, what seems to be missing even in a young family, where all domestic problems are solved from the outside. This is explained by those longing, the ever-increasing social needs. Therefore, the social protection of the interests of a young family in our country has risen to the level of Public Policy.

The Uzbek family is quite different from the family of other peoples. Often, several generations of members live together in the same family. From this, its structure becomes more complex: grandmother and grandmother (representatives of the older generation), father and mother (manifestations of the second

generation), older-younger children (members of the third branch), grandchildren and great-grandchildren (members of the fourth generation).

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